

Amenorrhea and it's Homoeopathic Management

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Abstract:- Amenorrhea literally means absence of menstruation. It is a symptom not a disease. The prevalence of amenorrhea is increasing day by day as the more no. of females are visiting gynaecologist due to this problem. When menstruation starts in a female it is called menarche and when the menstruation ceases or ends at the age of [45-50 yrs]in a female it is called menopause. Homoeopathy plays very important role in treating amenorrhea. Homoeopathy acts deeper at a dynamic level. Homoeopathy treats patient in a holistic manner as a whole rather than treating only disease.

Keywords:- Amenorrhea , homoeopathy.

I. DEFINITION

Amenorrhea refers to the absence of menstrual period either because periods doesnot started or they stop.

Amenorrhea is of two types:

Primary and Secondary amenorrhea

A. Primary Amenorrhea

Primary amenorrhea is the absence of menstruation in a young girl who doesnot get her first periods yet by age of 16 years. The normal upper age limit for menarche is 15 years.

➤ Causes

The causes of primary amenorrhea are grouped as follows:

- Hypogonadotropic hypogonadism
Delayed puberty, Hypothalamic and pituitary dysfunction, Kallmann's syndrome, Central nervous system tumors
- Hypergonadotropic hypogonadism
Primary ovarian failure, Resistant ovarian syndrome, Galactosemia, Enzyme deficiency (17 α hydroxylase deficiency)
- Abnormal chromosomal pattern
Turner's syndrome (45 X), Various mosaic states 45 X/46 XX, Pure gonadal dysgenesis (46 XX or 46 XY) , Androgen insensitivity syndrome (Testicular feminization syndrome)

- Developmental defect of genital tract
Imperforate hymen, Transverse vaginal septum, Atresia upper-third of vagina and cervix Complete absence of vagina, Absence of uterus in MRKH syndrome.
- Dysfunction of thyroid and adrenal cortex
Adrenogenital syndrome, Cretinism.
- Metabolic disorders: Juvenile diabetes.
- Systemic illness
Malnutrition, anemia, Weight los, Tuberculosis.
- Unresponsive endometrium
Congenital – Uterine synechiae (tubercular)

B. Secondary Amenorrhea

Secondary amenorrhea is the absence of menstruation for 6 months or more in a women in whom normal menstruation has been established.

➤ Causes

Causes of secondary amenorrhea are:

- Natural amenorrhea
During the reproductive age, female experience a amenorrhea phase which is due to natural or physiological reason such as: Pregnancy, Breastfeeding, Menopause
- Contraceptives.
- Medications
Some medications can cause secondary amenorrhea and these are: Antipsychotics, Cancer chemotherapy, Antidepressants, Blood pressure drugs, Allergy medications
- Lifestyle factors: Lifestyle factors which contribute to secondary amenorrhea, for instance are: Low body weight, Excessive exercise , Stress
- Hormonal imbalance: Hormonal imbalance can occur due to many medical problem, including: *Polycystic ovary syndrome* (PCOS), *Thyroid malfunction*, *Pituitary tumor*, *Premature menopause*

II. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

The amenorrhea in a female of reproductive age is due to one of the following: disturbance of normal hormonal, physiological mechanism, or female anatomic abnormalities. The normal physiological mechanism works by balancing hormones and providing feedback between the hypothalamus, pituitary, ovaries, and uterus.

During normal female menstruation cycle:

Fig 1:- Female Menstruation Cycle

The uterus then carry out the follicular and secretory phase of the menstrual cycle. Any defect at any level of this normal physiology of females can cause amenorrhoea.

On the other hand, any abnormality in the normal anatomy of the reproductive organs of a female can also cause amenorrhoea

III. CLINICAL FEATURES

Sign and Symptoms of amenorrhoea depends on the cause of amenorrhoea, the symptoms a female experience along with absence of menses are:

- Milky nipple discharge
- Hair loss
- Hirsutism
- Headache
- Vision changes
- Obesity
- Mood swings
- Bodyache
- Pelvic pain
- Acne

➤ Investigations

- Pregnancy test
- Thyroid test – TSH level
- Male Hormones tests
- Scans- X-ray, Ultrasound, MRI/CT SCAN
- Hormones tests – FSH, LH, Prolactin.
- Laproscopy
- Karyotype
- Blood tests

IV. MANAGEMENT

Primary amenorrhoea is treated by homoeopathy medicine when there are no anatomical abnormalities present. Otherwise primary and secondary amenorrhoea are both manageable by homoeopathy.

➤ Homoeopathic Therapeutics for Amenorrhoea

- **Pulsatilla** – Amenorrhoea. Delayed first menstruation. Menses – too late, scanty, slimy, painful, irregular, intermittent flow with intense pain. Suppressed menses from wet feet, nervous debility, or chlorosis. Pains spasmodic excite suffocation and fainting, must have fresh air.
- **Sepia** – Amenorrhoea at puberty. Bearing-down sensation as if everything would escape through vulva, must cross limbs to prevent protrusion. Menses irregular of nearly every form, early and profuse; sharp clutching pains.. Prolapse of uterus and vagina. Morning sickness. Leucorrhoea yellow, greenish; with much itching. Metrorrhagia at time of climaxis. Mania from profuse menses.
- **Graphites** - Amenorrhoea without any particular symptoms of malaise; vagina dry; occasional show of menses, which are pale and very scanty, with abdominal pains and pains in the limbs; burning and itching of labia during scanty flow; face pale and bloated.
- **Apis-mel** - Suppressed menses, with congested or inflamed ovaries menses stop suddenly or cease for two or three days, to begin again, blood black; dysmenorrhoea, with scanty discharge of slimy blood; ovarian cysts in women, especially widows with specific pains, soreness and stinging pains, tight feeling in abdomen and uterus, endometriosis.
- **Natrum-mur** - Menses irregular; usually profuse. Delayed first menses. Vagina dry. Leucorrhoea acrid, watery. Bearing-down pains; worse in morning. Prolapsus uteri, with cutting in urethra. Uterine cramps. Suppressed menses. Hot during menses. Menses too early and profuse or too late and scanty.
- **Conium mac.** – Menses too late, scanty, suppressed. Rash before menses. Dysmenorrhoea, with drawing-down thighs. Cancer of uterus. Menses absent. Induration of ovaries and uterus. Breasts become sore and painful before and during menses. Leucorrhoea thick, milky, acrid causing burning.
- **Sulphur** – Menses too late, short, difficult, thick, scanty, black, acrid making parts sore. Epistaxis during menses. Headache before menses. Leucorrhoea offensive, foul. Itching and burning in vagina. Suppression of menses from excitement it can be either mental or physical.

- **Senecio aureus** – Functional amenorrhea of young girls with backache. Suppressed menses. Leucorrhoea with headache. Leucorrhoea yellow. Premature and profuse menses. dysmenorrhea. Retarded menses. Sensation that menses would appear but they fail.

V. CONCLUSION

This concludes that amenorrhea is affecting many females in reproductive age, which is treatable by homoeopathic medicines, when medicine is prescribed according to guidelines given by Dr.Hahnemann in Organon of Medicine.

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